

WING DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS FOR LOW-ALTITUDE, LONG-ENDURANCE SOLAR-POWERED UAVS

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Abstract. In solar-powered drones, the design of the wing plays one of the most important roles. This article explores optimal wing design considerations to enhance the performance of these UAVs, focusing on high aspect ratio wings, lightweight structures, solar panel integration, and aerodynamic efficiency. Key design parameters and trade-offs are discussed, supported by calculations and theoretically analysed. The study aims to provide a comprehensive framework for optimizing wing design to achieve extended flight durations and operational effectiveness in low-altitude environments.

Keywords: solar-powered, UAV, aspect ratio.

INTRODUCTION

Solar-powered UAVs are increasingly utilized for long-endurance missions due to their ability to harness solar energy for extended flight times [1]. However, achieving optimal performance in low-altitude flight requires careful consideration of wing design parameters [2]. A solar UAV wing design usually focuses on maximizing efficiency, stability, and energy collection. The key solar UAV wing design considerations are given in the picture 1.

High Aspect Ratio Wings. These wings (picture 2) are long and narrow, which reduces drag and improves aerodynamic efficiency. They are especially beneficial for solar-powered UAVs as they help maintain higher speeds and longer flight durations [1, 3, 8].

Picture 1. Main solar-powered UAV wing design considerations.

Lightweight Structure. To maximize the benefits of solar power, the UAV needs to be as lightweight as possible. This often involves using advanced materials like carbon fibre composites and lightweight foams.

Solar Panel Integration. The wings should be designed to accommodate solar panels. This usually involves integrating the panels into the wing surface or attaching them in a way that maximizes exposure to sunlight [4].

Wing Shape and Airfoil. The wing shape (e.g., tapered or elliptical) and airfoil design (the cross-sectional shape of the wing) should be optimized for low drag and high lift-to-drag ratio. This helps in maintaining efficient flight over long durations.

Stability and Control. The design should include features that ensure stability and control, such as winglets or stabilizers. These features help in minimizing drag and improving overall flight performance.

Energy Storage and Distribution. Effective management of energy collected by the solar panels is crucial. The design should include efficient battery storage and power distribution systems to ensure that energy is used optimally [5].

Foldable or Retractable Wings. For practical deployment and storage, some solar-powered UAVs feature foldable or retractable wings. This allows for easier transport and storage without compromising aerodynamic performance during flight.

Cooling and Thermal Management. Solar panels and electronics can generate significant heat, so the design should include features for effective cooling and thermal management to prevent overheating.

Picture 2. Wing aspect ratio comparison.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

2.1. To assess the wing design, several key aerodynamic and structural parameters should be analysed. The following formulas should be used [6]:

Lift Coefficient (C_L):

$$C_L = \frac{L}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S}$$

where L is lift, ρ is air density, V is velocity, and S is wing area.

Drag Coefficient (C_D):

$$C_D = \frac{D}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S}$$

where D is drag.

Aspect Ratio (AR):

$$AR = \frac{b^2}{S}$$

where b is wingspan and S is wing area.

Wing Loading (WL):

$$WL = \frac{W}{S}$$

where W is weight and S is wing area.

2.2. Solar panel integration. Selecting the right type of solar panel is critical to maximizing efficiency and ensuring durability [4, 7]. Thin-film photovoltaic cells are often preferred due to their lightweight and flexible nature, which allows them to conform to the aerodynamic contours of the UAV wings. Monocrystalline and polycrystalline panels are also considered, though they tend to be heavier. The choice depends on the balance between energy efficiency, weight, and cost. The integration of solar panels can be optimized by designing the wing with an area dedicated to panel placement. Assuming a 22% efficiency for the solar panels, the total energy harvested is calculated based on solar irradiance at the UAV's operational altitude. For example, for a wing area of 1.2 m², the total energy collection per hour under full sunlight is approximately [4]:

$$E = 0.22 \times 1000 \text{ W/m}^2 \times 20 \text{ m}^2 = 4400 \text{ W}$$

Material selection. One of the primary considerations for UAV wing materials is their weight. The wings must be light enough to facilitate long-duration flights without excessive power consumption. Common lightweight materials include:

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs). CFRPs are favoured for their high strength-to-weight ratio and stiffness. They are crucial in maintaining structural integrity while minimizing weight. Their use, however, is often balanced with cost considerations.

Aramid Fibres (e.g., Kevlar). Kevlar is another lightweight material known for its high tensile strength and impact resistance. It is often used in conjunction with other materials to enhance durability.

Aluminium Alloys. Lightweight aluminium alloys, particularly those with high strength and fatigue resistance, are also employed. They offer a good balance between weight and strength, though they are heavier than CFRPs or aramid fibres.

Wing and airfoil shape. The planform shape of the wing significantly affects the UAV's performance. Common planform shapes include:

Straight Wings: Straight wings are simpler to manufacture and provide good stability at low speeds. However, they are less efficient in terms of lift-to-drag ratio compared to more advanced wing shapes.

Elliptical Wings: Elliptical wings offer a highly efficient lift distribution, which reduces induced drag and enhances aerodynamic performance. This shape is ideal for optimizing endurance but can be complex to design and construct.

Delta Wings: Delta wings provide high manoeuvrability and can support high-speed flight. However, they may not be as efficient at lower speeds and are typically used for different types of UAVs rather than long endurance applications.

Swept Wings: Swept wings help in reducing drag at higher speeds by delaying the onset of shock waves. They can be beneficial for UAVs that may transition to higher speeds, but for low altitude, long endurance flights, their benefits might be limited.

The airfoil, the cross-sectional shape of the wing, affects lift, drag, and overall aerodynamic performance [5]:

Cambered Airfoils: Cambered airfoils have a curved upper surface and a flatter lower surface, which generates more lift at a given angle of attack compared to a symmetric airfoil. This characteristic is beneficial for enhancing lift and efficiency during long-duration flights.

Symmetric Airfoils: Symmetric airfoils have equal curvature on both the upper and lower surfaces. They are more suitable for applications where the wing experiences varying angles of attack, but they generally provide less lift compared to cambered airfoils.

Thick vs. Thin Airfoils: Thicker airfoils can support more fuel or payload and provide better structural strength, but they may increase drag. Thin airfoils, on the other hand, reduce drag but may compromise on strength and payload capacity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For a low altitude, long endurance solar-powered UAV, the high aspect ratio wing combined with a cambered airfoil is typically the best design choice. This combination maximizes aerodynamic efficiency, reduces drag, and enhances lift, which is crucial for extending flight duration and optimizing the performance of solar-powered UAVs. This design approach balances the need for efficiency with practical considerations related to wing construction and operational performance.

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs) are generally the best choice for high-performance UAV wings due to their superior strength-to-weight ratio, durability, and thermal stability. They excel in providing the necessary structural integrity and efficiency for long-duration flights. However, if cost is a significant constraint or if specific performance characteristics are required, combining CFRPs with aramid fibres in a hybrid approach can offer a balanced solution.

CONCLUSION

The pursuit of optimal wing design for low altitude, long endurance solar-powered UAVs involves a careful balance of aerodynamic efficiency, structural integrity, and energy management. As UAVs are increasingly employed for tasks demanding extended flight durations and high operational efficiency, particularly in low-altitude environments, the design of their wings becomes crucial in achieving these objectives.

Aerodynamically, wings designed for low-altitude flight must enhance lift while minimizing drag. High-aspect-ratio wings are often preferred due to their reduced induced drag, which can contribute to longer endurance. However, the design must be adaptable to various environmental conditions and flight dynamics to maintain stability and performance. Incorporating wing shapes that offer optimized lift-to-drag ratios can significantly improve fuel efficiency and extend flight time.

The choice of materials plays a critical role in wing design, especially for solar-powered UAVs where weight reduction directly impacts performance. Advanced composite materials, such as carbon fibre-reinforced polymers, provide the necessary strength-to-weight ratio, allowing for both durability and reduced weight. This is essential for supporting the integration of solar cells without adversely affecting the UAV's aerodynamic properties.

Solar energy integration is another key consideration. The wing's design must facilitate effective solar panel placement while ensuring that the panels do not disrupt airflow or add excessive drag. The design of the wings should include considerations for solar panel orientation

and exposure, potentially incorporating adjustable elements to optimize energy capture throughout the flight.

Additionally, the effectiveness of energy storage systems cannot be overlooked. Efficient wing design must support not only the capture of solar energy but also its storage and management. Innovations in battery technology and energy management systems are crucial for ensuring that stored energy is used effectively to sustain long-duration flights.

The synergy between aerodynamic design, material selection, and energy management is fundamental to achieving optimal performance in low altitude, long endurance solar-powered UAVs. Future advancements in technology and materials will likely continue to drive improvements in these areas, enabling UAVs to operate more efficiently and effectively for extended periods. As research and development in this field progress, the ongoing refinement of wing design will be pivotal in enhancing the capabilities of solar-powered UAVs, making them more versatile and capable in a range of applications from environmental monitoring to long-term surveillance missions.

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